

pH-Metric Studies on the Ethereal and Ethyl Acetate extracted Blue Perchromates and their Decomposition Products*

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Barreswil¹, Moissan², Conick³, Riesenfeld⁴ and Wiede⁵ assigned acidic nature to the blue perchromate. R. Schwarz and H. Giese⁶ called it a peroxide with Cr_2O_5 formula. In discarding the acidic nature they studied its decomposition product and the pyridine complex.

Rai^{7,8} made further studies on the pyridine complex and the decomposition products and concluded that the blue compound is a peroxy compound of tervalent chromium having $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ formula.

No worker has studied the variation in pH of water during the decomposition of blue compound. pH of its various decomposition products has also not been studied. The present paper deals with such studies with a view to extrapolate the results for deciding the nature of the blue perchromate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The water used in the present study was always conductivity water. The reagents were either Analar or B.D.H. The blue perchromates and their various decomposition products were prepared as described earlier^{9,10,11,12}.

Study with the Water Decomposition Product.—About 25 ml. of water decomposition product was allowed to exchange with washed and dried Dowex 50(H) resin. 5 ml. of this exchanged solution was titrated iodometrically against standard thiosulphate solution (N/87). Another 5 ml. of this was oxidised by 30% H_2O_2 in alkaline medium and then titrated iodometrically after boiling off excess of H_2O_2 . In both the cases the titration value was same i.e., 4.1 ml.

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The strength of the unexchanged water decomposition product solution was brought at par (in terms of thiosulphate solution used) to that of the exchanged product solution. 5 ml. of this was titrated iodometrically against the same thiosulphate solution and another 5 ml. was titrated similarly after oxidising as above. The ratio between the titration values of the oxidised and unoxidised product solution was found to be 1:1.33.

Open and Closed Bottle Decomposition Products.—The open and closed bottle decomposition products of the ethereal and Ethyl acetate extracted decomposition products are insoluble in water. They however dissolve in dil. H_2SO_4 . pH study was not made with these products as the added acid will interfere.

pH Measurement.—20 ml. of each unexchanged solution was taken in a clean Pyrex beaker and the pH was measured. The solutions were then diluted with known volumes of conductivity water and the variation in pH was noted at various known dilutions. pH of the exchanged counterparts of each was also noted in the similar manner.

Variation in pH of water in contact with different samples of blue perchromates was also noted till complete decomposition in the following way: 20 ml. of the conductivity water was taken in a clean Pyrex beaker and its pH was noted. 20 ml. of each sample of the blue perchromate was added to the different beakers taken above. The variation in pH at definite intervals was noted till the blue compound decomposed completely. Observations are noted in the following tables:

pH measurements were made with expanded scale Beckmann pH meter.

TABLE I

pH of water decomposition products of various samples of blue perchromates

Resin :—Dowexo (50 (H) vol. of the W. D. P. solution taken for pH = 20 ml.

Temperature = 28°. 5 ml. of the W. D. P. solution (exchanged or unexchanged) requires 2.15 ml. of N/87 $Na_2S_2O_3$ solution.

Vol. in ml. of conductivity water added.	pH of W. D. P. (unexchanged) of blue perchromate; Etheral prepared with H_2SO_4 .	pH of W. D. P. (unexchanged) of blue perchromate; Etheral prepared with tartaric acid.	pH of W. D. P. (unexchanged) of blue perchromate; Ethylacetate prepared with H_2SO_4 .	pH of W. D. P. (exchanged) of blue perchromate; Etheral prepared with H_2SO_4 .	pH of W. D. P. (exchanged) of blue perchromate; Etheral prepared with tartaric acid.	pH of W. D. P. (exchanged) of blue perchromate; Ethyl acetate prepared with H_2SO_4 .
0	4.55	3.85	3.00	3.50	3.45	2.00
1	4.58	3.88	3.02	3.50	3.50	2.00
2	4.60	3.90	3.02	3.53	3.50	2.00
5	4.60	3.95	3.08	3.60	3.58	2.05
10	4.62	4.00	4.12	3.80	3.65	2.10
20	4.70	4.15	3.20	3.80	3.80	2.15
40	4.85	4.38	3.35	3.85	4.00	2.20
50	5.05	4.49	3.40	3.90	4.10	2.25
70	5.28	4.65	3.50	3.90	4.25	2.30
80	5.30	4.75	3.50	3.90	4.30	2.40
100	5.60	5.10	3.60	3.90	4.45	2.40

TABLE II

Variation in pH of water in contact with the different samples of blue perchromates

Strength of each sample of blue perchromate in terms of thiosulphate solution.
5 ml. of each sample requires 10.3ml. of N/87 $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution.

Temperature = 28°.

Time in minutes	pH of water in contact with		
	Ethereal blue perchromate prepared with H_2SO_4 .	Ethyl acetate blue perchromate with H_2SO_4	Ethereal blue perchromate prepared with tartaric acid.
0	6.90	6.90	6.90
3	4.60	3.90	4.35
5	4.58	3.90	4.32
10	4.58	3.85	4.30
40	4.40	3.70	4.20
60	4.30	3.70	4.18
90	4.20	3.68	4.05
105	4.00	3.60	4.05
140	3.82	3.52	3.90
150	3.75	3.42	3.75
130	3.70	3.40	3.70

DISCUSSIONS

pH measurement of the water decomposition products of the different samples of the blue perchromates clearly show that they are chromium compounds and not chromic acid solutions. There is a noticeable decrease in the pH when the product solutions are allowed to trickle through a cation exchanger(H) before pH measurement. Had this product been chromic acid, hydrogen ion concentration would have remained constant before and after exchange. The decrease in pH show that the chromium(III) of these products has been replaced by H of the resin.

This decrease in pH due to Cr(III) is supported by the qualitative examination of the elutriant with Diphenyl carbazide test^{13,14,15}.

pH of the chromium(III) compounds is nearly 4.5¹⁶. The metal being a member of transition group is less basic and hence its salts get hydrolysed like:

and thus the pH of these salts is on acidic side.

Taku, Uemura and Hideo¹⁷ have shown that even chromium complexes like amines or chlorine substituted amines have pH in the range of 3 to 4 at $\frac{1}{300}$ to $\frac{1}{500}$

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mole concentration. The pH of the decomposition products in the range of 3 to 4.55 is thus justified as these have been suggested to be chromium dichromate (loc. cit.)

According to Schwarz and Giese (loc.cit.) CrO_3 is the formula for the blue perchromate which according to them gives chromic acid on decomposition. Had this been the case, there would have been no decrease in pH on exchange with cation resin (H). Again the increase in the titration value has been shown earlier (loc. cit.) to be due to the conversion of Cr (III) present in these products into Cr(VI). Therefore, the explanation suggested by Rai and coworkers (loc. cit.) for the formation of these decomposition products (having trivalent and hexavalent chromium) by his formula $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ seems to be correct.

W. H. Hartford¹⁸ has observed that except for a small variation with temperature in dilute solutions, the effect of temperature, purity of acid and water on the pH of aqueous CrO_3 is negligible. The variation of pH with dilution as noted in above tables thus again show that the solution under examination is not chromic acid but chromium compound.

The variation in pH of the conductivity water has also been noted when in contact with the blue perchromates (Table II). The range of pH between 6.9 and 4.0 again show that the blue perchromate decomposes giving some chromium (III) compound and not chromic acid as in that case the pH would have been much lower.

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